

INSIDE THE MIND: AN ATHLETE'S MENTAL HEALTH JOURNEY DURING INJURY

by

Hailey D. Murdica

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Approved by:

Elaine M. Rutkowski, PhD, RN, CNS, PHN

Dr. Stacy Mallicoat, Director University Honors Program

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Hailey D. Murdica

0009-0007-5879-5183

California State University, Fullerton

Abstract

Athletes and their mental health during a period of injury is something that is rarely ever talked about. Specifically, their mental health during an injury. However, it is finally time that this changes. The literature includes studies that provide insight to just how detrimental an athlete's mental health during the time of injury can be. This project explores the mental health issues accompanying athletes as they travel through their injury process. The project collects data regarding the athlete's state of mind to examine the struggles underneath the surface of collegiate athletics. Interviews from five athletes from different sports on campus at California State University, Fullerton were the source of the data. There is a strong correlation of injuries to depression, and other mental health issues. However, student athletes all acknowledge that the final destination of their journey through injuries resulted in positive things, such as "patience", "control", and the "power of the mind".

Inside The Mind: An Athlete's Mental Health Journey During Injuries

Selfish. Immature. Sociopath. A shame to this country. These are all things that Simone Biles was called after removing herself from the Tokyo Olympics in 2020 due to mental health reasons. Growing up participating in gymnastics and watching Simone Biles become the greatest gymnast of all time, seeing these comments not only broke my heart but truly enraged me. I soon realized that reading this caused these two emotions for the same reason; the majority of people simply do not understand what it is like to be a highly competitive athlete. They do not understand the pressures that are placed on us. They do not understand what it is like to be seen more as entertainment than as human beings. They do not understand how anxiety-inducing it is to know that each performance dictates your place in the athletic world, let alone the respect you are given.

At the time of the 2020 Olympics, I was half way through my collegiate career as a 100m and 200m sprinter at California State University, Fullerton. Participating in college athletics is something that I will cherish forever, but that is not to say that it didn't come with an immense amount of stress. Just like the misunderstandings stated above, having an injury only added to those stressors as a highly competitive athlete. I have been injured plenty of times during my career as a division 1 sprinter, from pulled hamstrings to the career ending synovitis in my knee, requiring surgery that occurred in May of 2022.

During these times, even when my track and field career was crumbling before my eyes, no one really asked how I was doing mentally. The questions always revolved around my knee injury, the recovery, and if I was going to be able to run again. No one came to me and said, "Hey, I understand that this is a tough situation for you, here are some people you can talk to if

needed". It is clear that in the athletic world, there is a distinct stigma against mental health, especially when it comes to injuries. We are constantly supposed to be tough, determined, and resilient. There is no room or acceptance for anything less than that, which is why there is a significant lack of resources in collegiate athletics that can help athletes mentally during their time of injury. With injuries, the focus is constantly on rehabilitating the body as fast as possible to return to the sport. But what about rehabilitating the mind? Because of this lack of awareness and resources to help collegiate athletes, rehabilitating the mind, in my experience, is not even a thought while athletes are in the injury process.

Project Purpose

The purpose of this project is to bring awareness to those within collegiate athletics, and outsiders looking in, regarding the mental health issues that athletes go through as they travel through the injury process. Additionally, this project aims to be a voice for athletes in terms of telling their story and expressing a side of their injury that is so often suppressed.

Description of Project

To act on the purpose at hand, this qualitative project is coupled with a literature review that can give readers insight on the stigma around mental health in sports and how impactful on one's psyche sports can truly be. Interviews were conducted that will provide lived experiences of athletes as they travel through their injury process, connecting the physical attributes with the mental health journey that accompanied them. This project aims to apply to both male and female collegiate athletes to ensure that they are not alone, and their voices are heard, along with those involved in collegiate athletics with the hope to better support student athletes. Work on this project began in September 2022 and was concluded in May 2023.

Methodology

A literature review was conducted using California State University, Fullerton's library website using search terms including "mental health in elite athletics", "psychological response to injuries", "stigma on mental health in sports", and "mental toughness in sports" were used to find the articles. The search was limited to published, peer reviewed articles that were written in English within the past ten years. The chosen articles included research that was conducted in the United States and the United Kingdom,

In addition, five student athletes from California State University, Fullerton who all participated in different sports were interviewed by this researcher following signed consent. These interviews were recorded using the voice memos feature on an iPhone and were interviewee led. There was no script or predetermined questions, excluding the last question of their overall experience. Interviews evolved based on the athlete's lived experiences. Once recorded, the interviews were transcribed into Google Docs using Descript, where they were then manually coded, looking for themes that were present among all participants. Finally, male and female themes were analyzed for similarities in mental health attributes during their injury process to determine a general mental health journey during injuries.

Review of Literature

Mental Health and Athletics

It is common knowledge that athletics takes a physical toll on the human body. Along with Division 1 sports being physically demanding, studies have found that elite athletes have a higher risk of developing a mental disorder than the general population (Rice, et al., 2016).

Contributing to this greater risk includes athletes who are injured, nearing retirement, or having performance difficulties (Rice, M., et al., 2016).

To break down these mental health issues a little deeper, 37% of elite athletes report mild to moderate depression, 32% are poor sleepers, and 8% are high trait anxious (Sheehan, et al., 2018). As these issues can obviously be detrimental, 19% of elite athletes have reported an issue with alcohol misuse (Gouttebauge et al., 2019). Of all articles researched for this topic, all have identified that these mental health traits are often looked over.

Psychological Responses to Injuries

Oftentimes, people believe that during an injury, the physical aspects are the only thing that hurts. However, many studies, books, and journals have come to find that the body is not the only thing in pain. An athlete's mind tends to become completely strained as well, as discussed in Eugene Hong and Ashwin L. Rao's book titled, "Mental Health in the Athlete". Hong and Rao 2020 explain that in response to injury, there are cognitive, emotional, and behavioral aspects that the athlete goes through. They state that "the cognitive response to injury is how the athlete interprets their illness or injury. Cognitive responses lead to emotional responses, which then can affect an athlete's behavioral response, which can be the athlete's motivation, goal-setting abilities, compliance with treatment, and response to treatment". Hong and Rao also argue that there is a difference between "normal" and "problematic" responses to injuries. Nonetheless, these reactions are undisputable.

Other studies have commented on the "problematic" responses to injury. These responses include not eating because they "don't deserve to", depression, substance abuse, sleep disturbance, anger or rage, and emotional outbursts (Putukian,2016). Putukian adds that "emotional responses to injury are common, and problematic responses can be those that are

persistent, worsen or appear excessive”. In terms of returning to practice after adhering to these negative psychological responses during injury, successful return to play is deterred and often prolonged (Ivarsson et al., 2017).

The Stigma Around Mental Health in Sports

With so many clear mental health problems spiraling into the athletic world, one could inquire why these issues are still so prevalent. The answer stems from stories like Simone Biles’; the stigma around mental health in sports is silencing athletes from speaking out and getting help. Researchers are finding that the push for collegiate athletes to be “mentally tough” is often conflicting with pre-existing mental health issues during their sports (Liew et al., 2019). Coaches have argued that mental toughness is one of the most important psychological characteristics in order to be successful in elite sports (Liew et al., 2019). However, the “highly valued characteristics of mental toughness (e.g., perseverance and overcoming adversity) may mean that athletes are less likely to seek the mental health support they need, due to a fear of being treated differently or unfairly” (Bird et al., 2021).

Researchers are also noticing that part of this unwillingness to seek mental health support in collegiate athletics is due to the perfectionism that is hammered into its athletes. Perfectionists tend to have “reflecting concerns about making mistakes, feelings of discrepancy between one’s standards and performance, and negative reactions to imperfection” (Watson et al., 2021). Therefore, seeking mental health support can be seen as an imperfection to some athletes who struggle with perfectionism, thus causing the stigma that needing help is a “flaw”.

Results

Initial Injury to Action Taken

In the first part of the injury process, where athletes are initially injured then leading up to what they decide what is to be done about it, the main theme that emerged throughout the interview process was shock/ anger (see Table 1). However, we see these emotions in different ways. Athlete 1 expressed anger with the athletic training staff and stated, "...they kept saying it was nothing. And that's what really pissed me off, and that's why I had a love hate relationship with the trainers. I felt injured in November. I wasn't told that I needed surgery until like March or something of the next year, because I was going through the process of a sprained ankle, which is just recovery and stretching and all this stuff. But I could tell it wasn't getting better". Athlete 2 felt anger with the situation, expressing that, "I just got so frustrated that I tried to come back sooner than I was ready".

Meanwhile, athletes 4 and 5 experienced immense shock when their injury happened. Athlete 4 described the shock she felt when she reinjured herself as she said, "Then on my anniversary of the first tear, I'm talking the same day, same time, really only a few feet away from it, I tore the other, my left one. They always say that there's a high chance that if you tear one then you're going to tear the other one. But I didn't want to accept that. I just couldn't believe it, it really happened". In the same realm, Athlete 5, injured with a heart condition due to COVID, explained that, "In that moment, realizing there was actually something medically wrong with me was honestly a little shocking. You're taken aback for a second because you're not exactly sure how to take that, to be told that you have something that's basically incurable and they don't know what the effects are going to be. And so, it takes you a second to kind of come to terms".

During this first step in the injury process, although it is true that both men and women interviewees experienced shock and anger, there were differences between their reactions. With

the female athletes, results also saw that they felt annoyance and confusion. These feelings stemmed from the female athletes not being heard or listened to about the seriousness of their injuries. On the other hand, male athletes also felt denial, in which they refused to believe what was happening to them (Table 2).

Action Taken to Rehabilitation

In the next step of the injury process, the athletes have taken action to heal their injury and are enduring rehabilitation. However, from their stories, it is clear that more than physical injuries needed to be rehabilitated during this time as the most common theme was depression. Across all five athletes, heartbreaking statements were made, such as, “It was a very draining process because, you know, missing one day of practice is one thing. But missing weeks and months of it, you get very discouraged, and you think that you're never going to get back to your full power, full strength, and everything” from Athlete 1. Athlete 2 explained that “people don't really talk about it, but when you put your time and effort into something for so long, you are attached to that thing more than anyone could ever know. And not being allowed to do it is like a different level of pain. It causes some serious despair. Life is telling you no over and over again, and you're sitting here asking why, and you're not getting an answer”.

From the interviews, the depression can stem from other feelings as well, as Athlete 3 discussed how he was “really worried about being able to play and about the injury affecting me playing the rest of the season. So, I feel like that's the mental part that I struggled with”. Similarly, Athlete 5's depression derived from fear. Athlete 5 stated, “Knowing every day you go out to practice that there's a legitimate risk that you might not walk off the track that day is terrifying. I had a heart monitor on for a few weeks, and having that sit there and constantly remind me that I wasn't okay was pretty heavy and very draining emotionally”. Athlete 3

explained that while she was in rehabilitation, it “definitely has been draining. It's hard. I have days where I just don't want to come out to the field, or I don't want to even see (researcher redacted sport used here to preserve confidentiality). I love seeing the girls play, but it hurts me, you know?”.

During the second stage of the injury process, results again showed the difference between male and female characteristics (Table 2). With the female athletes, regret and frustration were prominent in their interviews regarding the actions taken and the lack of information in terms of their injury. The male athletes resorted to obsessing over their injury in order to get better as quickly as possible. For example, Athlete 2 stated that he “tried crazy methods. I started looking up things that could get me back sooner. I even considered getting a medical leech and taking the blood out of my foot, like some insane methods”.

Rehabilitation to Return to Sport

After the athletes have been through rehabilitation and their injury is healed, they enter a period in the injury process where they begin to attempt to return to their sport. From the interviews, athletes began to have hope, which is quite a mental turnaround from the depression they entered during the previous stage in the process. Athlete 3 explained that “taking baby steps” gave him the hope he needed, and he came back “more ready than ever.” In just a few weeks after the interview was conducted, Athlete 4 stated that she was going to try and get back on the field, and stated that she was “happy and looking forward to that”. Athlete 5 discussed that she found hope in the heart monitors that were given to her and the data that doctors were taking to figure out what was truly wrong. All athletes, both male and female, showed hope during this time (Table 2).

After Return to Sport

To finish off the injury process, athletes have returned to their sport, however anxiety and fear tend to loom over them. Every athlete that was interviewed felt “paranoid or fearful when they were fully cleared,” all due to different reasons. Athlete 2 explained that his fear stemmed from “being replaced”, while Athletes 1, 3, 4 and 5 all stated that their “anxiety came from reinjuring” themselves. Athlete 3 expanded on this, specifying that “even if it would hurt, even if it was just natural wear and tear over the season, I was scared. I would just think to myself, “I hope I just don't injure it again”, because then I would be out for way longer”. Athlete 4, with her return to sport coming so soon, expressed that she's “thinking that if I can easily tear it with these small movements, what is going to happen when I try something bigger? Something faster? It wasn't even contact. So, I feel like in the back of my head, I am going to have that fear of doing things”. With a heart problem, the anxiety hits a little deeper, as Athlete 5 revealed that “knowing every day you go out to practice that there's a legitimate risk that you might not walk off the track that day is terrifying. I had a heart monitor on for a few weeks, and having that sit there and constantly remind me that I wasn't okay was pretty heavy and very draining emotionally. With the frustration and the anger and the anxiety, you just burn out at some point and you have to give in”.

During the final stage in the injury process, all athletes, regardless of gender, exemplified feelings of paranoia, anxiety and fear (Table 2).

Athlete Takeaways

Although the mental health journey during the injury process can seem heartbreaking, painful, and upsetting, the athletes interviewed had some uplifting takeaways from their experiences. Looking at Table 1, the athletes felt things such as a new “power of the mind” and learned other things such as patience and self-control. Athlete 5 reflected this when she said,

“There's nothing that I cannot do. I'm the only thing that would stand in between me and achieving something”. Athlete 1 would agree, as she stated, “I think I'm more mentally strong than I thought”. Almost all the athletes felt that “trusting the process and not being rushed back into returning to the sport” was their most important lesson learned. Athlete 4 stated, “Trusting the process and working hard was something I learned I had to keep my mind on”, while Athlete 3 expressed, “it's obviously hard but it could be for the better just to sit and wait it out until it gets better, just so you don't re-injure it more. So, I just feel like that's one thing that I took away from that. Frustrating, but necessary”. Likewise, Athlete 2 stated that “I think now I'm a little bit more patient for the most part. Nothing's perfect. I'm not perfect. You can't expect everything to go that way that you want, you know?”.

Discussion

Based on the review of literature found within the past ten years, there is a clear mental health problem in the collegiate athletic world. Not only are researchers identifying that being an elite athlete causes immense stress, but they are also discovering that being injured causes the athlete to sink to a whole other level. When an athlete is injured, they have psychological responses just as they do physical ones, where these responses can hinder their return to “play.” These problems continue to worsen as the stigma surrounding mental health and seeking support in elite athletics remains dominant.

Although there is a distinct mental health path that athletes go through during the injury process, emotions that were felt still differed depending on an athlete's gender and their lived experience. Female athletes felt more annoyance and shock in the way that athletic officials did not take their injuries seriously, whereas male athletes never had this issue as they reported that they were always believed. Female athletes tended to “feed off” of each other's energies of

depression during time of injury, while male athletes became obsessed with their injury, even resulting in extreme methods to get better as quickly as possible.

Regardless of the differences between male and female emotions, all athletes that were interviewed were able to find positives in a negative situation. When asked about their takeaways from this experience, all athletes commented on “feeling more balanced, learning control, and understanding how mentally strong” they really are. Each athlete acknowledged that their “final destination” was a “light at the end of a dark tunnel”.

As it is obvious that there is much going on with an athlete during a time of injury that is not just physical, the lack of resources for student athletes needs to be addressed. Why are athletes not being asked how they are doing mentally and emotionally? Why are resources not being offered to an athlete during their injury process? Unfortunately, these questions can be answered simply: people do not care. As athletes are seen as just a body to perform, their mental health is pushed aside and the stressors that come with injury are never treated or even acknowledged. It is with high hopes that this project brings awareness to such an important topic.

Conclusion

This project reflects the mindset of a group of Division 1 athletes as they experience their mental health journey during the injury process. Five male and female athletes from all different sports in the California State University, Fullerton athletic department were interviewed to examine experiences with injuries and mental health throughout athletics. The athletes were not prompted with questions, but told their story based on their recollections in an unstructured interview. Although this project created a clear path, it also exemplified a clear distinction in which males and females react differently to injuries depending on which point in the process they are in.

The results of this project could potentially help all sport professionals. From coaches to athletic trainers, this project can aid in handling athletes and their injuries in a better way. Simply treating the body is not enough anymore. With the male and female comparisons that were found, an athlete's treatment can be even more specialized if coaches and athletic trainers can understand how they react differently. Rehabilitation of the mind and the body during the injury process needs to be the new standard of practice.

Appendix

Interviews

Athlete 1: So, I think it all started when I was at a tournament in Nevada. I kept rolling my ankle and I thought it was nothing. And then the more that it happened, the more that it hurt even more and more. And whenever I went to the trainers, he said you just sprained, just sprained it. And we never really went into a deeper dive on the situation. And I knew that I was bad because it didn't feel like a normal problem. So, I ended up having a peroneal tendon subluxation. And so basically there's like a little hook on my tendon that keeps it in. And I tore that so my tendon in the back of my ankle bone would snap over. And I would literally feel it happen. Anything I did, and at first it was just when I was actually playing tennis, and that's when I felt it the most. But then it was when I'm just walking, when I'm doing the bare minimum. And so, I told the trainers, "This does not feel good". So then one of the athletic doctors finally took a look. So, they did an ultrasound and found out that I had a tear. And so, they tried to find other ways to heal it, other solutions rather than surgery. And the first thing was PRP injections.

They're horrible. They're literally the worst decision ever. They take your own blood, and then they put it back. I felt like I was a turkey and it was the worst pain of my life. It did absolutely nothing. I had to get it after two weeks each, and I think it helped for like maybe a week, but then as I progressed, I tried to do more, and it just went right back to how it was.

So that summer, this is 2020, I decided to get surgery. I got it in the beginning of June and I was in a cast and a boot for like a month and a half, maybe two. That was very horrible and showering sucked.

I was so paranoid, I thought everything was going wrong. Um, and then I got it off. I had to get used to walking and putting pressure on it. I started going to physical therapy and at first, I thought it was stupid because I had to learn how to walk again. I had to learn how to jump on my heels and I was like, oh my gosh, this is so easy.

It was a process. It was a very draining process because, you know, missing one day of practice is one thing. But missing weeks and months of it, you get very discouraged, and you think that you're never going to get back to your full power, full strength, and everything.

And I think when I went back to school in August, till around like early September, mid-September, it was very slow, I had to just sit in a chair and just hit strokes for tennis. And then slowly, surely, I was getting my ankle taped. I was getting a brace and everything, and I think I was healed much faster than I thought, but I wasn't mentally healed.

I was so scared to do anything. I was so scared to move too fast going in any direction. And I think that's what really stopped me.

Interviewer: Do you think during that time, did you feel a push from your coaches? You weren't mentally ready yet, were your coaches supportive in that?

Athlete 1: I think they were really supportive, especially because my assistant coach, she had pretty much the exact injury and she still wears ankle braces to this day. But she knew exactly what I was going through, so that really helped me a lot.

Interviewer: How long did it take the trainers, or whoever was looking at your ankle, to realize it was more than just a sprained ankle? Because for a long time you felt it was something more from the get-go, right?

Athlete 1: Yeah. And they kept saying it was nothing. And that's what really made me angry, and that's why I had a love hate relationship with the trainers. I felt injured in November. I wasn't told that I needed surgery until like March or something of the next year, because I was going through the process of a sprained ankle, which is just recovery and stretching and all this stuff. But I could tell it wasn't getting better. But they just told me to keep going, keep going. So, I'd do stem and ice and all that stuff and then I was thinking, "this does not feel right".

Interviewer: Do you think if they would've taken your feelings and how you knew how your body felt more seriously that you could have been healed sooner?

Athlete 1: I think so. It was a partial tear; it wasn't even a full tear. But you know, the more that I played on it, the more that I stressed it, it kept going and I wish I never went through injections. That was like almost a month or two of my time. Obviously, I never would've imagined surgery and I never wanted it, but if I could have had it sooner and not go through the PRP, I would've been much better off.

Interviewer: How was it mentally to go through two rounds of PRP and see no changes?

Athlete 1: It was tough, and I had a teammate as well who was getting the exact same injections in her wrist, and she felt nothing as well. It was a good thing to have her, but then it was a bad thing because when we were both down, we just wallowed together. Just feeding off of each other with these horrible thoughts.

Interviewer: Do you have any takeaways from the experience in general? Mentally, did you learn anything about healing processes, the mental aspect of things?

Athlete 1: I think I'm more mentally strong than I thought. I had a really good support team. Like my teammates were always worried about me. If I, if I always said like, oh, I'm kind of hurt. They're like, no, no, no. Like please don't do anything. And I really appreciated that. And same as my coaches, they really put me as a person before an athlete, and I appreciated that a lot.

Interviewer: What was it like to watch your teammates progress while you were still healing?

Athlete 1: Having to take one step forward and three steps back was really tough. They were always progressing and getting better and having to just sit back and watch, knowing I can't control anything was terrible. That's just a part of the process. Anyone who gets injured, you know, you just have to start from scratch. That's really tough. And I always thought about that, like seeing people progress or like they're doing so well and sometimes if they're doing really well and we are winning, I'm like, okay, well maybe I should just stay back, maybe they don't need me. You start to spiral.

End of Interview

Athlete 2: I would say that one of my worst injuries was back in high school, and it was during my football season. Basically, what happened was one day during practice, we were just going through some drills, you know, tackling drills and such. I'm not sure exactly how it happened, but I remember I hit my foot on something and overnight a bruise started to form. I just could not walk on that foot. I actually had to get crutches and a whole boot. It was just insane. I think the mental toll of that one was especially tough because I was so passionate about that sport.

I seriously wanted to go to the NFL at the time. So, it felt like every second that I wasn't practicing felt like a year of not training. I felt like people were passing me, people were getting better than me. While I have to sit on the sidelines. The mental toll of that was hard because I considered that to be my career, my livelihood. I considered that to be everything and having to sit on the sideline, go into practice, but not practicing. Talking with teammates, but never really relating, you know, for however long on a mystery injury that I still don't to this day, don't even know how I got it, you know? It hurt, there were some times that I cried, there were some times when I just got so frustrated that I tried to come back sooner than I was ready. I tried crazy methods. I started looking up things that could get me back sooner.

I even considered getting a medical leech and taking the blood out of my foot, like some insane methods. And people don't really talk about it, but when you put your time and effort into something for so long, you are attached to that thing more than anyone could ever know. And not being allowed to do it is like a different level of pain. It causes some serious despair. Life is telling you no over and over again, and you're sitting here asking why, and you're not getting an answer.

So, it's tough. It doesn't seem like much, on the outside people just think, "come back when you're healed, who cares?". But to us, it's not like that. It's definitely more.

Interviewer: Do you think that not knowing what exactly the injury was or how it happened made things worse?

Athlete 2: Oh, absolutely. You know, a broken bone, you know what to do, you know how long to wait, you know everything about that. But with this, I didn't really get so lucky. I would rather have a broken bone than what I had, because then at least I would know how to fix it. But I had no clue what to do about it. Doctors couldn't help me. The internet couldn't help me.

Interviewer: So, what did you do about it? Did you just wait? Did you go through pt? What did you do to try to heal?

Athlete 2: I honestly just waited. I massaged my foot, to try and help ease the pain and after about three or four weeks, give or take, I was back. But I was still kind of behind everybody. I didn't get much playing time that season. It kind of nurtured the fears and the worry about being injured, you know? Because everything that I didn't want to happen kind of came true in a way.

The thing about football is, it's not so much a performance-based sport. It is, but it isn't. You rely a lot on your coaches. Your coaches have to know that they can trust you when they put you in, you know? And yeah. They don't really like to roll that dice because that kind of loses games in a way. So, when you aren't really in the spotlight, you aren't really showing your coaches time in and time out that you know that you're performing. They're going to forget about you, even if they like you, they might just look at the next guy. And it's not so much a biased thing, it's really just how the sport goes. That's the way life is. And so, in a lot of other sports, it's the same way. When you take so much time off, people kind of forget about you, you know? There's a lot of things that kind of weigh down on athletes when they get injured.

Interviewer: Do you have any takeaways from this experience? Do you feel like you learned anything?

Athlete 2: I learned that obsession is blinding. I learned that there is such a thing as too much passion, you know? I learned that life is about balance. Balancing what you can and can't control. Because too much of anything is a bad thing. I've had more injuries since that point, and I think now I'm a little bit more patient for the most part. Nothing's perfect. I'm not perfect. You can't expect everything to go that way that you want, you know?

End of Interview

Athlete 3: I believe it was the first conference game last year, and I went up to go pass the ball, but the dude thought I was going to shoot it and he landed on me, and I twisted my ankle. Well, I sprained it and I was out for about a month. I was just hoping it wasn't worse than what it was. But then during, when I was actually injured, I really just worried about being able to play and about the injury affecting me playing the rest of the season. So, I feel like that's the mental part that I struggled with.

Interviewer: Because it was early on, you said it was the first conference game, right?

Athlete 3: Yeah. So, I didn't know if I was going to be able to go back in time. But it was only for about a month or so. When I came back though, I was always worried about whether I was going to re-injure it or tweak it again or something.

Interviewer: Did you have to do physical therapy for it? What was the recovery process like after you twisted it?

Athlete 3: Yeah. I had to do physical therapy. I went to the trainers and really worked on every day. Then stem, ice, band workouts to help with resistance. We did that for a whole month straight and then it ended up getting better and good enough, and then really wearing a brace the rest of the year to help support it.

Interviewer: How did you feel coming back after? It was technically healed, but did you feel any resistance trying to come back mentally?

Athlete 3: Yeah, for sure. Because sometimes, even if it would hurt, even if it was just natural wear and tear over the season, I was scared. I would just think to myself, "I hope I just don't injure it again", because then I would be out for way longer.

Interviewer: How long did it take you to feel comfortable again with your body and doing all the movements correctly?

Athlete 3: About two to three weeks. Because at the end of the day, I'm playing the sport, so there's always a chance for injuries. So, I'm not going to let it really sit there on my mind and mess up my game while I'm playing.

Interviewer: Do you have any takeaways from the experience? Anything that you kind of learned throughout the process of it?

Athlete 3: Yeah definitely. You know, it's obviously hard but it could be for the better just to sit and wait it out until it gets better, just so you don't re-injure it more. So, I just feel like that's one thing that I took away from that. Frustrating, but necessary.

End of interview

Athlete 4: So, I have torn my ACL twice now. I tore the first one in 2021. And that, the first one was obviously hard for me because I didn't know what to expect. I didn't know what I was going into. All I heard was that it was one of soccer's biggest injuries. So, I went into it very blindsided, and I took it very hard mentally. I really cried every day. And then on top of that, my surgery stitches got infected, so I had to be hospitalized for two weeks.

I was constantly on new medication and they opened me up three more times just to clean it. It sucked even more because every time they would clean it, I was thinking, "oh, that's the last time they're going to open me up". And then they would come back like four hours later when I had just walked again. They said they were so sorry but they had to take me in again, so the back and

forth was really hard for me. Once I was able to overcome those issues, it got a little easier. I think I just got into the process of going to PT every day and going into CAPS (therapy).

I was learning to deal with it. And, my teammates, they're all so sweet to me. I think that helped me overcome some things. They're my family, so when I came back, I came back strong. I was looking forward to getting back on the field.

Then on my anniversary of the first tear, I'm talking the same day, same time, really only a few feet away from it, I tore the other, my left one. They always say that there's a high chance that if you tear one then you're going to tear the other one. But I didn't want to accept that.

I just couldn't believe it, it really happened. You know the feeling, when you tear it once so you know when it happens again. So, when I felt it, I automatically thought, "Dang, there it is". At that time, we were at a training camp in Chula Vista. But I was so mentally gone at that point that I left early. I had to go back home. I had to figure it out.

So, I met with Nate (a PT at CSUF) and he checked me out and he confirmed it was torn. So, then I just was a disaster for the first month. I couldn't believe it, but also, I was getting my surgery done right away. So that was one thing I was looking forward to, at least I could just get it done as soon as possible.

But because I was kind of accustomed to things, mentally I was a lot better for the second one. I still struggle here and there, on the 17th, which is next week, March 17th, I hopefully get the okay to start doing field work, just no contact. So, I'm so happy and I'm looking forward to that.

But overall, mentally it definitely has been draining. It's hard. I have days where I just don't want to come out to the field or I don't want to even see soccer. I love seeing the girls play, but it hurts me, you know?

Interviewer: During that period, did you go to practices and games? How was that?

Athlete 4: So, for the first one, I kind of disappeared from everyone. And my teammates were sad about it actually. They wondered where I was and noticed that I wasn't coming to practices or games. So that kind of made me think, for the second one, that I need to be there with my team. They actually did miss me. I guess I realized that I do have an impact on the team even though I'm not playing. So, during the second one I attend every practice and it's kind of helpful because it gets me out of bed. I feel like with the first one I was just wanting to stay in bed all day. I'm happier now. The girls get me out there and they're funny.

Interviewer: Did you feel pressure from the coaching staff to come back? Or any pushback from staff about fears of coming fully back?

Athlete 4: Honestly, they're all very sweet, and nice to me, but they did want me back on the field. I knew that, so if anything, I put more pressure on myself than they did. They always told me that they wanted me to be a 90-minute player and such. So, I kind of put that in my head so I pressured myself with those words, you know? But I feel now with the second one, I don't think

that's the case. I think they're going to take it very, very seriously. Seriously and slow because they don't want it to happen again.

Interviewer: Next week you get to try some field work, do you have any reserves going into that?

Athlete 4: Yeah, I'm kind of scared. With the first one, I tore it when pulling the ball back and my knee just kind of gave out. And then with the second one, I hopped up and landed on my left one and it kind of gave out. So, I'm thinking that if I can easily tear it with these small movements, what is going to happen when I try something bigger? Something faster? It wasn't even contact. So, I feel like in the back of my head, I am going to have that fear of doing things. But I can't always be thinking that way because then I'm never going to come back right the way I want to. I just got to keep working hard on my quad, my strength so that it doesn't happen again.

Interviewer: Do you have any takeaways from the experience, anything that you feel like you learned about in the process of things?

Athlete 4: Definitely. For me, it was hard because I felt like I was getting in shape just to get out of shape. So, I learned a lot about my body and how it reacted to exercise and eating. But the back and forth was so mentally draining. I had a lot of issues with my body and wanted to wear baggy clothes all the time because I was self-conscious. So, I learned a lot about eating healthy and what my body can take in. The biggest one I learned though was patience. Trusting the process and working hard was something I learned I had to keep my mind on.

End of Interview

Athlete 5: So, I remember when we returned from COVID and first started practices, I remember feeling lightheaded and I remember passing out on the field and thinking that I was just out of shape. I figured it was just hot. And then as time continued and I kept doing that, kept passing out, I was still in denial that there was anything medically wrong with me. I figured that I had just not worked out enough over the quarantine. But it ended up being that the COVID I had contracted during quarantine had some bad side effects. But I didn't understand how bad until I had gotten COVID again and I had to do a comeback test. My EKG didn't come back perfectly clean. But I figured that it was just some sort of minor issue until I got referred to a cardiologist.

They were the ones who told me that my tests were not coming back completely normal. But they didn't know exactly what was wrong. All they knew was that what was happening to me was happening to other athletes who were getting COVID and that what was most likely wrong with my heart was COVID related and they wouldn't be able to do anything about it.

At that moment, realizing there was actually something medically wrong with me was honestly a little shocking. You're taken aback for a second because you're not exactly sure how to take that,

to be told that you have something that's basically incurable and they don't know what the effects are going to be. And so, it takes you a second to kind of come to terms.

There is no set-in stone comeback plan. There's no “you're going to go to PT for this amount of time and you're going to do this certain regiment and you'll be back in this timeframe”. It's just open water. And so that confusion is really unsettling and it creates a lot of anxiety.

Then when you get back to practice, you realize you can't do all the workouts that you used to do, and you can't be the athlete you used to be and you know that you'll probably never be that person again. It gets frustrating. It gets hard. I mean, I remember sitting there during some of the workouts and being a captain on the team, I want to be a leader.

I want to show the girls how you finish a workout, how you face diversity and how you break those lactic acid walls. And I couldn't. At some points, it was really frustrating because I felt like a failure having to just stop and sit on the bench because I wasn't allowed to finish the workouts.

But at the same time, I had to understand that if I did continue that workout, I did risk going into cardiac arrest. And that was a pretty serious thing for me to have to consider. I was angry for a while because it's not something I could have controlled. It's not something that I could have been like, “well, if I stretched more or if I ate better...”. This was something that was completely out of my hands and there's nothing I could do to change it either.

So, you want to be mad, but you have nobody to be bad at, which kind of makes it more frustrating that you have nothing you can blame. Then it hits the point where this is just the situation now and I have to continue. I have to continue my career as an athlete, but with these certain circumstances and it becoming draining, it becomes pretty hard.

Knowing every day, you go out to practice that there's a legitimate risk that you might not walk off the track that day is terrifying. I had a heart monitor on for a few weeks, and having that sit there and constantly remind me that I wasn't okay was pretty heavy and very draining emotionally.

With the frustration and the anger and the anxiety, you just burn out at some point and you have to give in. There's nothing you can do about it. I can feel all these emotions and everything, but at the end of the day, they're not going to change anything. I have the heart condition I have now and that's how it's going to be. And so eventually, I just had to accept it. My teammates know that I'm here to work hard. They know that if I could finish the workout, I would finish the workout. With my new limits and my new parameters, I've grown to just kind of accept my heart problem as part of me, but it definitely affects my day-to-day living.

I do have to be careful of the things I agree to do. I can't go on long hikes like I would want to. I mean, it's hit the point where I was so sick and tired of being sick and tired that I just kind of gave up on worrying about it. I gave up on the frustration and the anxiety and I've hit a point where this is me now and this is how I have to be.

Interviewer:

So, giving you the heart monitor, that was what they decided they were going to do about the situation? Just try to monitor it as best as they could and go from there? So, was that their sense of a form of PT as they would for a physical body injury?

Athlete 5: Yeah, they decided that they were going to go ahead and try every test that they could think of to try to see if they could figure out what was wrong with me. That was part of the heart monitor trying to see if they could pick up any unusual rhythms or anything, any issues with my breathing.

But when they would gather the data and put it together and they couldn't find anything that would match an already existing diagnosis, they decided that we'd kind of put together a pseudo plan. The little bits and pieces we took from each test we put together. We figured out some things such as that I can't do long endurance runs, that if I put my feet upside down and I needed more blood and oxygen to my head, that that would help.

So, each test gave us a little bit more information and we were able to put together a plan. That kind of served as my physical therapy.

Interviewer:

Any takeaways from the experience in general? Did you learn anything? Besides what to do with your heart, anything like how to go towards things, how to handle things?

Athlete 5: I definitely have to say that this has to be one of the most pivotal moments in my life because I don't think I will ever be able to recreate the feeling of pushing yourself beyond your limits other than like getting on a track and knowing you might not walk off. I now understand how in control of my own actions I am and how powerful my own mind can be in controlling what I do. And that has really translated to the rest of my actions. I can really make myself do whatever I want to do. There's nothing that I cannot do. I'm the only thing that would stand in between me and achieving something. And that really solidified when I'm the one who's making myself run on that track. I was given the option to medically retire and I said no. And that was my decision.

Interviewer:

Because this one isn't like a regular injury, would you say it is harder or easier to get through than say something with your back or something with a hamstring, like an injury that is more concrete?

Athlete 5: I would say this was definitely harder, um, since I have had a lot of regular injuries and I've had career ending injuries like my back. It's easier because you know you're going to get better. You know that you know that you're going to fully heal. But with my heart, I had one of the best cardiologists look me in the eyes and tell me, “We don't know what to do with you. There's only five people in this whole hospital that have what you have, and we don't know what to do with them”.

I've had multiple doctors look me in the eye and say, “we're just going to have to wait until further research comes out”. And that's the scary part, I just have to wait for research to come out and hope that it says that I can get cured. And I hope that it has options for me, but it's hard and it's lonely that nobody else feels how I feel.

It's kind of hard-to-find sympathy and find someone who relates to someone who has a heart condition at 21.

End of Interview

Tables

Table 1: Qualitative Themes

Athlete:	1 (Female)	2 (Male)	3 (Male)	4 (Female)	5 (Female)
Initial Injury	Anger Annoyed	Confusion Anger	Worried Anger Denial	Shock Blindsided	Shock Denial Confusion Anxiety
Action To Fix	Regretful	Frustrated Obsession Despair Bargaining	Obsession	Frustrated Despair Depressed	Frustrated Skeptical
Rehab	Depressed Drained Discouraged Unnecessary Hopeful	Worry Depressed Excited	Frustrated Eager	Depressed Shock Hope	Highs/lows of testing things Scared

Return to Sport	Scared Paranoid Spiraling	Fear of being replaced	Paranoid	Scared Spiraling Fear	Frustrated Scared Anger Anxiety
Takeaways from experience	Power of the mind	Balance Open Minded	Patience	Learned about own body Patience	Control Power of the mind

Table 2: Emotions

Men's Characteristics	Women's Characteristics
Confusion Anger Obsession Bargaining Denial Depression Worry Fear Excitement Eager Paranoid Hopeful	Anger Annoyance Depression Drained Discouraged Unnecessary Hopeful Scared Paranoid Shock Denial Frustration Confusion

Poster

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